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Enzymatically Degradable, Starch-Based Layer-by-Layer Films: Application to Cytocompatible Single-Cell Nanoencapsulation

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ABSTRACT: Cytocompatible formation and degradation of nanofilms in a controlled fashion has great potential in biomedical and nanomedicinal fields, including single-cell nanoencapsulation (SCNE). In this paper, we report the fabrication of biodegradable nanofilms with cationic starch (*c*-ST) and alginate (AL) by layer-by-layer (LbL) assembly and its application to the SCNE. The multilayer LbL nanofilms of *c*-ST and AL on individual *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, as well as on the flat gold surface, degraded on demand in a cytocompatible fashion by the treatment of α -amylase. The degradation profiles were investigated, with systematic changes of α -amylase concentration, by several surface characterization techniques, including quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (QCM-D) and spectroscopic ellipsometry. DNA impregnation in the LbL assembly formed DNA-loaded nanofilms, which showed an enzymatically controlled release of DNA. Highly cytocompatible nature of the film-forming and -degrading conditions was verified in the shell formation and degradation of *S. cerevisiae*. We believe that the cytocompatible, enzymatic degradation of *c*-ST-based nanofilms paves the way for developing advanced biomedical devices with programmed dissolution *in vivo*.

1. INTRODUCTION

Layer-by-layer (LbL) films with degradable characteristics have been fabricated for various applications including drug delivery systems, tissue engineering, and prosthetic devices.¹⁻³ In biomedical applications, the self-assembling materials in the LbL process are preferred, if not required, to be compatible with biological entities (e.g., proteins and cells), not doing any harm to them, and so are the fabrication conditions.⁴ These biocompatible materials and films also have recently caught significant attention in the emerging field of single-cell nanoencapsulation (SCNE).^{5,6} The biocompatible LbL films also could act as a reaction platform for postfunctionalizations, exemplified by SiO₂ or TiO₂ formation under physiologically relevant conditions.⁷⁻⁹

Nature-derived polymers are the strong candidates for a biocompatible and also degradable material.^{10,11} Among them, marine polysaccharides, such as alginic acid, chitosan, chondroitin sulfate, heparin, and hyaluronic acid, have intensively been employed in the formation of LbL films, because of their diversified chemical compositions and properties.¹² Especially, the varied charge identities and degrees in marine polysaccharides make them suitable for electrostatically formed LbL films:^{13,14} for example, alginic acid is negatively charged at the neutral pH,^{15,16} and chitosan is positively charged.^{17,18} In comparison, starch, the most abundant polysaccharide in the plant, has limitedly been used for the formation of LbL films, presumably because of its low charge density.¹⁹⁻²¹

Starch is mainly composed of amylose and amylopectin.²² Amylose is an $\alpha(1\rightarrow4)$ -linked, linear

polymer of α -D-glucose,^{23,24} and amylopectin is a branched, α -D-glucose-based polymer with additional $\alpha(1\rightarrow6)$ glycosidic bonds for branching.²⁵ Starch degrades into monomers, dimers, and oligomers, in the organism, by the action of various enzymes.²⁶ For example, α -amylase, present in the pancreas and salivary gland, randomly hydrolyzes the $\alpha(1\rightarrow4)$ -glycosidic bonds and breaks the starch chain down to dextrans, maltose, and glucose. Amyloglucosidase, found in the small intestine, hydrolyzes the $\alpha(1\rightarrow4)$ -glycosidic bonds at the non-reducing ends of starch. Isoamylase is an isoenzyme of α -amylase and cleaves the $\alpha(1\rightarrow6)$ -glycosidic bonds of starch. The plant has β -amylase, which hydrolyzes $\alpha(1\rightarrow4)$ -glycosidic bonds at every 2 glucose units to produce maltoses only, in the vacuole and mesophyll cell chloroplasts. Numerous microbes produce the amylases aforementioned, and these microbial amylases are active under harsh conditions, such as high temperature, and acidic and basic solutions.

The enzymatic biodegradation of starch has led to numerous studies on its applications to food packaging and paper manufacturing.²⁷ In the biomedical and nanomedicinal applications, starch-based polymers also would be better functional, compared with the polysaccharides mainly derived from marine species, by considering the presence of the various starch-digestive enzymes in the human body as well as in other organisms. Herein, we fabricated the LbL films of starch and alginate for the formation of enzymatically degradable nanofilms and its application to the SCNE. The controlled degradability of the films was also applied to enzyme-triggered drug release with DNA as a model. To the best of our knowledge, this report is the first case of the LbL shells that degrade under cytocompatible conditions in the SCNE.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Materials. Starch from wheat, sodium alginate (AL), α -amylase from *Aspergillus oryzae*, acetic acid, bisBenzimide H 33258, deoxyribonucleic acid sodium salt from salmon testes (DNA), disodium phosphate, ferric chloride hexahydrate ($\text{FeCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$), fluoresceinamine, fluorescein diacetate (FDA), glycidyltrimethylammonium chloride, hydrochloric acid (HCl), monosodium phosphate, 3-(*N*-morpholino)propanesulfonic acid (MOPS), propidium iodide (PI), sodium acetate, sodium chloride (NaCl), sodium hydroxide (NaOH), tannic acid (TA), tris hydrochloride (Tris-HCl), and 11-mercaptoundecanoic acid (MUA) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Hydrogen peroxide was purchased from Samchun. 1-(3-Dimethylaminopropyl)-3-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC) and *N*-hydroxysulfosuccinimide sodium salt (NHS) were purchased from TCI chemical. Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid disodium salt (EDTA) and sulfuric acid were purchased from Junsei. Yeast extract peptone dextrose (YPD) agar and YPD broth were purchased from Duchefa Biochemistry. Deionized (DI) water (18.3 M Ω cm) from Milli-Q Direct 8 (Millipore) was used.

2.2. Synthesis of Cationic Starch (*c*-ST). Starch was functionalized to have cationic charges by the base-catalyzed, ring-opening reaction of glycidyltrimethylammonium chloride. Starch (1.5 g) was dissolved in 150 mL of DI water and stirred at 90 °C for 1 h. NaOH (0.5 g) was then added to the starch solution, followed by dropwise addition of a glycidyltrimethylammonium chloride solution (591 μL , 90%). The resulting solution was kept at 70 °C for 18 h, and 1-M HCl was added to lower the pH value below 7 to terminate the reaction. The solution was cooled to room temperature, and the polymer was precipitated by adding excess ethanol, dissolved in DI water,

dialyzed (molecular-weight cutoff: 3500) for 3 days, and lyophilized for another 3 days. The *c*-ST was characterized by ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy (D₂O, 400 MHz) and elemental analysis.

2.3. LbL Fabrication of *c*-ST and AL on Gold. Gold substrates were cut into the square shapes and cleaned with the piranha solution (3:1 mixture of hydrogen peroxide and sulfuric acid). The MUA self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) were formed on the gold substrates by immersing in an ethanolic solution of MUA (1 mM) for 18 h, washing with ethanol, and drying under the flow of argon gas. The MUA-primed gold substrate was immersed for 4 min in a *c*-ST solution (0.1 mg/mL in a 0.1-M acetate buffer, pH 4.5), washed with the 0.1-M acetate buffer (pH 4.5), immersed for 4 min in an AL solution (0.05 mg/mL in the 0.1-M acetate buffer, pH 4.5), and washed with the 0.1-M acetate buffer (pH 4.5). This deposition process formed one bilayer of *c*-ST/AL, and the process was repeated up to five times.

2.4. Quartz Crystal Microbalance (QCM) Analysis. The LbL deposition of *c*-ST and AL was monitored with a quartz crystal microbalance with dissipation monitoring (QCM-D) (Q-Sense Pro). Gold-coated AT-cut quartz sensors (Q-sense, ref QSX 301) were used as an LbL substrate. The excitation of multiple overtones was examined: 1st, 3rd, 5th, 7th, 9th, 11th, and 13th, corresponding to 5, 15, 25, 35, 45, 55, and 65 MHz, respectively. The adsorption process was performed with 0.1 mg/mL of *c*-ST and 0.05 mg/mL of AL (both in the 0.1-M acetate buffer, pH 4.5). For rinsing between depositions, the 0.1-M acetate buffer (pH 4.5) was used. Each polyelectrolyte solution was flushed for 4 min at a constant flow rate of 50 μL/min, and the rinsing solution was flushed for 3 min at the same flow rate. The QCM-D analysis was

performed up to the five bilayers of [*c*-ST/AL] ([*c*-ST/AL]₅). After fabrication of [*c*-ST/AL]₅, an α -amylase solution (1, 20, 300, or 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in the 0.1-M acetate buffer, pH 5.5) was flushed at a constant flow rate of 50 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$.

2.5. DNA Release. DNA was loaded into the LbL films by constructing [*c*-ST/AL]₄[*c*-ST/DNA]₃ films. The DNA solution of 0.1 mg/mL in the 0.1-M acetate buffer (pH 4.5) was used for the LbL deposition of DNA. After 30 min of film stabilization in the 0.1-M acetate buffer (pH 4.5), the DNA-loaded LbL films were immersed in the α -amylase solution (20 or 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in the 0.1-M acetate buffer, pH 5.5). The blank acetate buffer was used as a control. An aliquot of 40 μL was collected at the predetermined time point and gently mixed with 400 ng/mL of bisBenzimide H 33258 solution in a 2 \times TNE buffer (20-mM Tris-HCl, 0.4-M NaCl, 2-mM EDTA), and the fluorescence intensity was measured by fluorescence spectrometry ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 346 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 460 \text{ nm}$). The experiments were performed in triplicate.

2.6. Single-Cell Nanoencapsulation (SCNE). A single colony of yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, ATCC18824) from the YPD agar plate was picked and cultured in YPD broth media with gentle shaking at 33 °C for 30 h. The yeast cells were washed with DI water three times and dispersed in DI water. For priming the cells with the Fe³⁺-TA complex, to an aqueous suspension of yeast cells (490 μL) were added 5 μL of the aqueous TA solution (40 mg/mL) and 5 μL of the aqueous FeCl₃·6H₂O solution of (10 mg/mL) sequentially with 10 sec of vigorous mixing between the additions. After additional vigorous mixing for 10 sec, 0.5 mL of MOPS buffer (20 mM, pH 7.4) was added to the cell suspension for the pH stabilization, resulting in the formation of stable Fe³⁺-TA complex. For LbL-shell assembly of *c*-ST and AL, the Fe³⁺-TA-primed yeast

cells were washed twice with phosphate buffer (PB) (0.1 M, pH 5.8), and were alternately immersed in the PB solution of *c*-ST (1.6 mg/mL) and that of AL or FITC-AL (0.8 mg/mL) for 5 min each. The cells were washed with the PB solution after each LbL step. The alternate deposition was repeated to make the [*c*-ST/AL][*c*-ST/FITC-AL]₃ shell. For the viability assay, 5 μL of the FDA solution (10 mg/mL in acetone) and 2 μL of the aqueous PI solution (1 mg/mL) were added to the yeast suspension (1 mL). The resulting yeast suspension was incubated for 20 min, washed with the PB solution, and characterized by confocal laser-scanning microscopy (CLSM).

2.7. Characterizations. The synthesized *c*-ST compound was characterized by NMR spectroscopy (Inova) operated at the ultrashield of 400 MHz with deuterium oxide. The film thickness was measured with a spectroscopic ellipsometer Elli-SE (Ellipso Technology). The wavelength range of light was 400 to 700 nm, and the film-optimized model system was used for the variable refractive index. Four different points of each sample were measured, and average values were recorded. Fourier-transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were recorded with a nitrogen-purged Thermo Nicolet Nexus FT-IR spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher). The spectra were equalized by adding approximately 4000 scans for background and each sample. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) images were taken in tapping mode with an INNOVA-LABRAM HR800 (Horiba Jobin & Bruker). Contact angle measurements were performed using a Phoenix 300 goniometer (Surface Electro Optics Co.) equipped with a video camera. The static contact angle of a 3-μL water droplet was measured at four different locations on each sample. The fluorescent images were obtained with an LSM 700 confocal laser-scanning microscope (CLSM, Carl Zeiss).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Synthesis of Cationic Starch (*c*-ST). LbL self-assembly is one of the most widely and intensively employed methods for the construction of degradable thin films.²⁸⁻³⁰ It is based on the alternate deposition of materials, driven by complementary interactions between the materials- for instance, electrostatic, hydrophobic, and hydrogen bond interactions. The degradable LbL multilayer films, in principle, could be designed and fabricated on demand with any polymer combinations for substrates of any shapes, if the self-assembling materials for the films have sufficient and specific interactions with each other. Starch would be a promising base material for LbL film formation because of its natural abundance, and intrinsic biocompatibility and biodegradability, but the neutral glucose backbone in starch, having only hydroxyl (OH) groups, has precluded its wide acceptance in the LbL self-assembly. In this work, we used a starch derivative that had positive charges on its backbone, *c*-ST.³¹ Wheat starch was heated to 90 °C for gelatinization, loosening the globular structure of the starch by releasing strong intramolecular hydrogen bonds, and cationized by the base-catalyzed, ring-opening reaction of glycidyltrimethylammonium chloride. The ¹H NMR spectrum showed the characteristic proton peaks for the starch backbone at 5.4 (s, 1H), 3.72-3.84 (m, 4H), 3.54-3.62 (m, 2H) and 3.4-3.48 (m, 2H) ppm, and the peaks from the attached trimethylammonium ($-NMe_3^+$) chain were observed at 3.19 (s, 9H) and 4.38 (s, 1H) ppm (Figure S1a). The elemental analysis of freeze-dried samples indicated that *c*-ST contained 1.61% of nitrogen, corresponding to 0.287 of the degree of substitution (Figure S1b).

3.2. LbL Film Formation of *c*-ST and Alginate. The LbL-assembled films were fabricated by

alternately depositing *c*-ST and AL on a gold surface primed with the MUA SAMs (Figure 1a). The presence of *c*-ST and AL in the films was confirmed by FT-IR spectroscopy (Figure 1b). The absorption bands for C-O-H, C-O-C, and O-H groups in the *c*-ST backbone were observed at 1050, 1155, and 1320 cm^{-1} , respectively, and the band of C=O stretching, from the carboxyl groups in the mannuronate and guluronate residues of AL, was done at 1600 cm^{-1} . The band intensity increased with the number of bilayers, additionally indicative of the successful film formation of *c*-ST and AL.

Figure 1. (a) Schematic representation for LbL film formation of cationic starch (*c*-ST) and alginate (AL) and α -amylase-triggered film degradation. (b) FT-IR spectra of $[\text{c-ST/AL}]_n$, $n = 1, 3, \text{ and } 5$. (c) A graph of film thickness vs. a number of bilayers. (d) AFM micrographs of $[\text{c-ST/AL}]_n$, $n = 1, 3, \text{ and } 5$.

The growth of films ($[c\text{-ST/AL}]_n$) was followed by the ellipsometric-thickness measurement (Figure 1c). The film thickness was measured to be 1.1 nm for $[c\text{-ST/AL}]_1$ and increased to 11.2 nm for $[c\text{-ST/AL}]_5$. Figure 1c also showed the exponential film growth, similarly to the previous studies of poly-L-lysine- and chitosan-based LbL films.^{32,33} The observed exponential-growth characteristics in our system implied that excess *c*-ST or AL could freely diffuse into the interior of the multilayer film during its deposition process. The polymers in the film also could come out to the film surface and enable the additional adsorption of the incoming polymer.¹³ In other words, the adhesive forces between polymers in the solution and on the film surface are relatively stronger than the cohesive forces between polymers in the film. The strong interactions between *c*-ST and AL would lead to the formation of polymer complex structures upon drying, which was visualized by the AFM. The AFM images, accordingly, showed that the $[c\text{-ST/AL}]_5$ films had islet structures (Figure 1d), and the root-mean-square roughness (RMS) gradually increased from 1.48 to 3.97 nm with the number of depositions.

The LbL process of *c*-ST and AL was further characterized in detail by QCM-D measurements, which allowed for real-time monitoring of film deposition. Figure 2 shows the changes in the seventh overtone of frequency ($\Delta f_{7/7}$) and dissipation (ΔD) during the five-bilayer deposition, respectively. The frequency ($f_{7/7}$) decreased discernably upon the injection of the polymer solution (*c*-ST or AL), indicating that *c*-ST or AL was successfully adsorbed onto the substrate. The film formed was stable, and the introduction of the washing buffer did not cause any frequency changes. The $\Delta f_{7/7}$ data clearly confirmed that the films were formed durably from-polymer-by-polymer in the course of five-bilayer deposition steps, making $[c\text{-ST/AL}]_5$. On the

other hand, the observed increase in the D value, which is defined as the sum of the oscillation-energy losses in the system caused by the interaction between the film and the medium, implied that the *c*-ST/AL films interacted strongly with the aqueous solution and had soft and viscous properties. This characteristic was similar to our previous report with chitosan and hyaluronic acid.³⁴ We thought that the film softness resulted from the strong interaction of the polymers with water, as well as hydration or swelling of the film. Accordingly, the water contact angles for [*c*-ST]₅[AL]₄ and [*c*-ST]₅[AL]₅ films were measured to be 18.8° and 15.5°, respectively, compared with 87.5° of the bare gold substrate (Figure S2).

Figure 2. A QCM-D graph with frequency (*f*) and dissipation (*D*) changes. The 5 bilayers deposition of *c*-ST and AL was monitored. The arrow 1 indicates the injection time for *c*-ST, and the arrow 3 for AL. The arrows 2 and 4 indicate the rinsing step with the acetate buffer (pH 4.5).

3.3. Enzymatic Degradation of *c*-ST/AL LbL Films. The enzymatic degradation of LbL films has several advantages over other degradation methods. For example, the enzymatic reaction degrades its target molecules selectively and provides spatiotemporal control over the degradation reaction. It also does not affect or harm to other surrounding entities and ensures

non-toxic or non-inflammatory responses, which is highly beneficial in the biomedical applications. Moreover, unlike other hydrolytic reactions, it is much rapid, enabling precise control of degradation characteristics. Because of the substantial advantages, the enzymatic degradation of LbL multilayers has widely been attempted in drug delivery systems and other biomedical applications.³⁴⁻³⁶ More importantly, it would contribute profoundly to the emerging field of the SCNE, where individual living cells are to be encapsulated with cytocompatible materials, preferably in a reversible fashion.^{37,38}

We investigated the enzymatic-degradation behavior of [*c*-ST/AL]₅ films with α -amylase, which randomly cleaves the $\alpha(1\rightarrow4)$ -glycosidic bonds. We envisioned that the presence of α -amylase in saliva would lead to the potential development of mouth strips in drug delivery systems.³⁹ The four different α -amylase solutions (concentration: 500, 300, 20, and 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) were prepared with the acetate buffer (0.1 M, pH 5.5) for the degradation studies. The QCM-D analysis (Figure 3a) clearly showed that the degradation reaction occurred more rapidly as the enzyme concentration increased. For example, in the case of 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, we noticed very rapid film degradation, and most of the films (88%) were degraded in 15 min. It is to note that the topmost layer in the film was alginate, not starch; however, α -amylase enabled the film degradation. The degradation behavior was also examined by the ellipsometric-thickness measurements (Figure 3b). In the α -amylase solution of 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ was degraded 92% of the film in 5 min of incubation. The film degradation was enzyme-specific: hyaluronidase and α -glucosidase, as negative controls, were not capable of degrading the films, and these enzyme treatments caused no significant thickness change like a blank acetate buffer of pH 5.5 (Figure S3). The FT-IR and AFM characterizations further supported the successful enzymatic degradation of the *c*-ST/AL

films (Figures S4 and S5).

Figure 3. Characterizations of film degradation by α -amylase with different concentrations: (a) frequency changes in QCM-D and (b) ellipsometric-thickness changes. Control: 0.1-M acetate buffer (pH 5.5).

3.4. Application to Controlled Drug Release: DNA. After confirming the enzymatic degradation of the c -ST/AL film, we investigated the enzyme-induced biomolecule release behavior of the c -ST/AL film, for the potential application to stimuli-responsive drug delivery systems. Specifically, we loaded the DNA to the $[c\text{-ST/AL}]_4$ film by performing an additional LbL process and formed $[c\text{-ST/AL}]_4[c\text{-ST/DNA}]_3$. The release of DNA from the film was measured by fluorescent spectrometric analysis with bisBenzimide H 33258 as a DNA detecting

agent. The result showed that most of the DNAs were rapidly released in 15 min upon the film exposure to 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ of α -amylase, and the lower α -amylase concentration (20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) slowed down the release rate (Figure 4a). The results arguably confirmed that the DNA release was enzymatically controlled.

Figure 4. Characterizations of DNA release from the $[c\text{-ST}/\text{AL}]_4[c\text{-ST}/\text{DNA}]_3$ film. Graphs of (a) the accumulated amount of released DNA vs. degradation time and (b) relative thickness vs. degradation time.

The enzymatic DNA release was additionally supported by the film-thickness changes. The

thickness of the $[c\text{-ST/AL}]_4[c\text{-ST/DNA}]_3$ film decreased to 11.4% in 5 min with 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of α -amylase (Figure 4b). In the control of blank buffer solution, the $[c\text{-ST/AL}]_4[c\text{-ST/DNA}]_3$ film maintained about 87.4% of its thickness even after 240 min. Notably, the thickness reduction behavior of $[c\text{-ST/AL}]_4[c\text{-ST/DNA}]_3$ showed a similar tendency to that of $[c\text{-ST/AL}]_5$, indicating that the DNA molecule had a negligible effect on the film degradation. Taken all together, these results suggested that the α -amylase-triggered drug release system could be applied to various therapeutic compounds incorporated into the $c\text{-ST}$ -based LbL films. In addition, this LbL-based drug delivery platform could be placed on various surfaces, like implantable devices, which are applicable for varied biomedical applications. For example, the triggering enzyme, α -amylase, exists in the mouth and pancreas, and could be utilized for the target release *in vivo*.⁴⁰

3.5. Application to Single-Cell Nanoencapsulation (SCNE). Previous reports arguably indicate the intensive and wide use of the LbL process in the SCNE.^{6,41,42} The advantages of the LbL methods in the SCNE include the potential in the formation of cytocompatible shells on individual living cells in a controlled mode, and in the introduction of the new functions that are not innate to the cells encapsulated. Various LbL pairs of biocompatible building blocks, such as chitosan, gelatin, or poly-L-lysine as a cationic polymer and alginate or hyaluronic acid as an anionic polymer, have so far been employed for the LbL-based SCNE.⁴³⁻⁴⁵ However, shell degradation still remains one of the missing pieces, because it is critically required that the conditions for shell degradation be cytocompatible, not doing any harm to living cells.^{37,38} Previous examples of degradable shells in the SCNE could be found, such as the shells of metal-organic complex,⁴⁶⁻⁴⁹ but there have been no reports on LbL-based, biodegradable shells. Shell degradability is highly preferred, if not required, for increasing the applicability and usability of

the cells encapsulated for the temporal protection.

In the SCNE, shell-degradation conditions should be cytocompatible, not to mention conditions for the shell formation. Based on the results with the gold substrate described in the previous sections, we envisioned that the *c*-ST-based LbL approach would be applied advantageously to the degradable SCNE: the films degraded rapidly under physiologically relevant conditions. We exploited the formation and enzymatic degradation of *c*-ST-based LbL shells on individual *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (baker's yeast) as a model. *S. cerevisiae* was chosen, because it had been one of the widely used cells in the SCNE.⁵⁰

The LbL shells of *c*-ST and AL were formed on *S. cerevisiae*, after priming the cells with Fe³⁺-TA complex by following our previous protocol,⁴⁶ in the PB solution (pH 5.8). For the easy visualization of the formed shells by confocal laser-scanning microscopy (CLSM), we used fluorescein-linked AL (FITC-AL) as an LbL component of the [*c*-ST/AL][*c*-ST/FITC-AL]₃ shell. The CLSM images of the resulting encapsulated yeast, yeast@*c*-ST/AL, clearly showed the ring-shaped, green fluorescence, confirming that *c*-ST and AL (and FITC-AL) were successfully deposited onto the cell surfaces, forming the *c*-ST/AL shells (Figure 5a). After shell formation, the cytocompatibility of the cell-forming process was investigated by the cell viability assay with fluorescein diacetate (FDA) and propidium iodide (PI). FDA, used as a viability probe for measuring the intracellular esterase activity and cell-membrane integrity, is hydrolyzed into green-fluorescent fluorescein. PI (red) intercalate between the bases in the intracellular DNA, which only happens with the cell membrane disintegration. The FDA-PI assay showed the viability of 97.6% (Figure 5b), which was significantly higher than the previously reported LbL-

based SCNE with synthetic polymers. For instance, the LBL shell made of poly(allylamine hydrochloride) and poly(styrenesulfonate) had 85% of viability even after 2-bilayer formation.^{51,52}

Figure 5. Single-cell nanoencapsulation. (a) CLSM images of yeast cells (top) after shell formation and (bottom) after shell degradation. (b) Cell viabilities after shell formation and degradation. The encapsulated cells were treated in 10 min with α -amylase (500 μ g/mL).

To investigate the biodegradability of the *c*-ST/AL shell, we incubated yeast@c-ST/AL for 10

min in the α -amylase solution (500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in 0.1-M PB solution (pH 5.8)). No ring-shaped fluorescence was observed in the CLSM images after α -amylase treatment, confirming the enzymatic degradation of the *c*-ST/AL shell (Figure 5a, right image). More importantly, the shell-degradation condition proved highly cytocompatible: no noticeable decrease in the cell viability was observed after shell degradation (Figure 5b). These results clearly confirmed that the *c*-ST-based LbL shell was successfully formed on and degraded from individual yeast in the highly cytocompatible manner, which is the first demonstration of degradable LbL shells in the SCNE.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we designed and fabricated the starch-based LbL nanofilms, which showed the controlled degradability with a starch-digestive enzyme, α -amylase. The cytocompatible shells of *c*-ST and AL were successfully formed on the surface of individual *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, and the rapid shell degradation by α -amylase was achieved without any compromise in viability. In the SCNE field, our system has several advantages, in addition to the ones from LbL approach per se: (1) The shell degradation is fast, requiring 10 min in the demonstrated case. Many previous works needed hours of incubation for shell degradation. The incubation time for shell degradation could be controlled more tightly in our system; (2) The conditions for shell degradation is astonishingly cytocompatible. Because of the use of enzymes, the conditions ensure the complete cytocompatibility unless the degraded entities are cytotoxic. Other chemical methods could not compete with the enzymatic method; (3) Starch is cytocompatible and potentially yields the nutrient, glucose. The formation of degradable LbL films has used

potentially toxic polymers, such as antimicrobial chitosan,⁵³ which could not be applied to the microbial SCNE. In addition, starch degradation into glucose would make the encapsulated cells survive in the nutrient-deprived conditions.

We demonstrated, in this work, the controlled degradation of the starch-based LbL nanofilms with α -amylase only, but there are many other starch-digestive enzymes derived from different sources in nature. Therefore, we believe that the spatiotemporal control of film degradation would be made possible with the starch-based LbL films, which provides substantial potential in the biomedical applications that require cytocompatible film degradation *in vitro* and/or programmed dissolution *in vivo*.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information. Reaction scheme, ¹H-NMR spectrum and elemental analysis of cationic starch. Digital photographs of the water droplets on *c*-ST/AL films. Graphs of ellipsometric-film thickness with hyaluronidase and α -glucosidase, and various pH values. AFM images and FT-IR spectra of the [*c*-ST/AL]₅ film after degradation. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

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Author Contributions

H. C. Moon, J. H. Park, J. F. Mano, and I. S. Choi conceived and designed the experiments. H. C. Moon, H. Cho, and H. Choi fabricated various chemical surfaces. H. C. Moon and J. Borges analyzed various chemical surfaces. H. C. Moon, S. Y. Han, and S. Han performed biological experiments. H. C. Moon, J. H. Park, J. F. Mano, and I. S. Choi co-wrote the paper. All the authors commented on the paper.

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